

Mental Health Changes During Fitness Training: A Narrative Review of Psychological Stages, Challenges and Coping Strategies

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Abstract

This narrative review explores the psychological stages of mental health adaptation experienced during fitness training, synthesising current findings from sport psychology, clinical mental health, behavioural science, and motivational theory. The review identifies four core stages - Motivation and Goal Formation, Early Progress and Reinforcement, Plateau and Burnout Risk, Identity Shift and Emotional Integration - each characterised by distinct emotional patterns, risks, and coping demands.

Findings highlight that mental health outcomes in training are not static or universally positive but evolve across time, shaped by motivation type, goal orientation, social context, and individual psychological flexibility. While early stages may foster empowerment and identity growth, plateaus and over-identification with fitness goals can trigger perfectionism, anxiety, or burnout.

This paper advocates for emotionally literate coaching, stage-specific mental health interventions, and inclusive fitness environments that promote resilience and psychological safety. It also identifies research gaps in long-term emotional monitoring, intersectional representation, and the role of digital influences in shaping training experiences.

The proposed model offers actionable insights for psychologists, personal trainers, and public health professionals, encouraging a shift from performance-based training toward sustainable, wellbeing-oriented frameworks.

Keywords: fitness psychology, mental health, motivation, resilience, burnout, training identity, exercise behaviour, coping strategies, psychological stages

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1. Introduction

In the contemporary health field, the benefits of regular physical activity for mental health have been widely recognised. Fitness training today is associated with improvements in mood, reduction of depression symptoms and anxiety, and enhancement of cognitive function (Warburton & Bredin, 2017). However, much of the currently existing literature presents only a static view of mental health outcomes, often suggesting that the psychological benefits of exercise are linear, predictable and universally positive (McKinney et al., 2016). This perspective on fitness neglects the complex, dynamic psychological journey that a person will experience by engaging with training.

Fitness training is not just about physiological changes; it is also a psychological process of changes that starts with shifting emotional states, growing motivations, and identity development. People beginning their fitness journey often experience psychological ups and downs corresponding to different stages of their training cycle (Gill et al., 2017). Motivation at the beginning can be on a high level, enhanced further by enthusiasm and specific goals to achieve. However, as time passes, challenges like setbacks, psychological and physical fatigue can happen, affecting mental wellbeing in significant ways (Crews et al., 2016). The mental health trajectory during training is understood as a set of stages instead of a consistent trend.

Recognising psychological and emotional stages linked with fitness training is vital in developing a more holistic approach for promoting exercise, coaching and mental health support systems. Traditional models like the Transtheoretical Model of Behavioural Change highlight how vital psychological readiness and maintenance are in physical activity (Liu et al., 2018). Similar frameworks from sports psychology promote motivation, goal adjustment, and mental resilience as critical factors for sustaining a good level of performance and well-being (Hacker & Mann, 2017). On top of this, there is an existing need to integrate those models into a wider understanding of mental health adaptation across the whole training process.

Various research studies suggested that different stages of training distinct psychological responses. The early stages of fitness training often present high motivation and optimism, powered by initial progress and satisfaction with new routines (Gjestvang et al., 2020). As training progresses, participants encounter moments where physical improvements slow down, and psychological challenges like frustration, self-doubt, followed by decreased motivation happen (Cachón-Zagalaz et al., 2023). Without having proper coping strategies or support

mechanisms, these psychological challenges can lead to situations of emotional distress, disengagement from fitness training and in some cases, the development of behaviours of overtraining or exercise dependence (Back et al., 2019).

Understanding these mental health stages during fitness training is essential for academic interest and practical implications for fitness professionals, psychologists, and public health advocates. Identifying common emotional stages that a person is undergoing during training can make interventions better timed and tailored to address specific psychological needs at each stage. Fitness trainers and coaches should be knowledgeable about basic mental health literacy. They can be critical in promoting psychological resilience by normalising setbacks, promoting emotional flexibility and encouraging adaptive coping strategies (Prochnow et al., 2020). Similarly, clinical psychologists and various healthcare professionals can use these insights to design programs that acknowledge the emotional complexities of sustained fitness participation.

This narrative review aims to search and explore the psychological evolution people can experience during fitness training, synthesising current research literature on mental health outcomes, motivation dynamics, and coping frameworks. The paper is structured around four key psychological stages of the training period:

- Motivation and Goal Formation;
- Early Progress and Reinforcement;
- Setbacks and Burnout Risk;
- Identity Shift and Emotional Integration.

Each stage will be examined in terms of everyday emotional experiences, associated mental health risks, and evidence-based coping strategies. Special research attention will be given to resilience models, self-compassion frameworks, and behavioural interventions that support long-term mental wellbeing in fitness.

By framing fitness training as a dynamic psychological process, this narrative review seeks to contribute to a broader understanding of how mental health goes alongside physical engagement. In doing so, it will advocate for a shift in how fitness participation is approached. Beyond a simple statement that exercise improves mental health, towards a more realistic and practical model of psychological support within fitness culture.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Psychological Benefits of Fitness Training

Regular physical activity is often associated with many mental health benefits, including reducing the level of stress and symptoms of depression or anxiety,

improving mood and enhancing cognitive function (Alam & Rufo, 2019). Many cross-sectional studies have demonstrated that exercise can function as a protective factor against mental health disorders, especially when participation in fitness is consistent and internally motivated. The mechanisms underlying these benefits include neurochemical changes, particularly increased production of endorphins and neurotransmitters, for example serotonin and dopamine (Bhattacharya et al., 2023).

When structured, fitness training offers people a sense of purpose, achievement and routine, all recognised as psychological stabilisers (Ma et al., 2024). This is particularly present in early engagement phases, where individuals often report increased feelings of empowerment and body satisfaction. Overall, emotional regulation is also increased. Those initial improvements are necessary for establishing a positive pattern of behaviour and reinforcing long-term exercise level of adherence and engagement (Ricardo et al., 2024).

Psychological benefits are not only physiological in nature but also deeply fitted in psychological construct as perceived competence, self-efficacy and personal agenda (Wang & Ashokan, 2021). The existing act of creating, setting and achieving fitness goals contributes to a growing sense of mastery, and this is crucial in developing mental resilience against pressure created by day-to-day life (Mishra et al., 2024). When people can see and observe their progress, whether by increased strength, endurance or consistency, they reinforce a self-image grounded in control, effort and personal capability. This experience can improve confidence in other domains of life like work, relationships and academic performance (Yorks et al., 2017).

In addition, regular exercise routines can help with emotional regulation. Research studies have shown that regular engagement in moderate to intense physical activity levels can significantly improve emotional awareness, reduce reactivity and promote better coping strategies (Alam & Rufo, 2019). The connection of mind and body in some fitness practices like strength training or cardiovascular endurance routines has been linked with increased interoceptive awareness, the ability to recognise and understand internal body signals. In exchange, it supports psychological stability and reduced anxiety symptoms (Almarcha et al., 2022).

Fitness training introduces further opportunities for social interaction and community belonging, which are considered protective factors for mental health. Participating in group classes, gym environments, or online fitness sessions can contribute to a sense of inclusion and support (Heinrich et al., 2022). This social engagement can create a structure of accountability and emotional encouragement that can result in enhanced adherence and increased motivation among participants.

Some evidence also suggest that fitness training can contribute to long-term reductions in negative thoughts and self-perception through attentional control mechanisms during physical effort (Wang et al., 2025). Exercise can offer individuals not only a temporary mood boost but also a sustainable tool for managing mental health.

2.2 - Psychological Risks and Challenges Across the Training Journey

Despite well-documented benefits of fitness training, it can also present psychological risks, mainly when participation is motivated by external pressures, perfectionism or aesthetic ideals (Ednie & Stibor, 2017). Several studies have identified that when exercise behaviours are driven primarily by appearance-related goals, persons are at higher risk of developing body dissatisfaction, exercise dependence and anxiety disorders (Reinboth et al., 2022).

Cognitive factors, including maladaptive perfectionism, fear of failure, and negative self-perception, often cause fitness engagement vulnerability to psychological strain (Gulle et al., 2014). These vulnerabilities can also interact with environmental stress and pressure, like social comparison, trainer expectations, or social media fitness culture, increasing the risk of mental health challenges during critical training phases.

Psychological risks often stay hidden under a surface-level culture of positivity in the fitness sector, where physical progress is celebrated. Still, mental health is frequently stigmatised or dismissed as a lack of discipline (Seddighian et al., 2020). The existing ethos that there are no gains without specific sacrifices can inadvertently normalise psychological distress, encouraging individuals to push through emotional discomfort without having a proper reflection of the level of support. This mindset, once placed in practice, can lead to emotional suppression and increased vulnerability to mental fatigue, frustration or self-blame, particularly during periods of overtraining or performance stagnation.

In some cases, the created tool of fitness engagement can be compounded by social validation loops that are common on digital platforms. For example, someone who shares progress images or achievements online can start equating their self-worth with public recognition. This will increase anxiety about maintaining an ideal appearance or performance level (Carrotte et al., 2015). Created pressure to keep visible success and result in compulsive exercise behaviours, social withdrawal or extensive reliance on distress mechanisms, including this disordered eating or body checking (Gjestvang et al., 2021).

Any potential injury or illness during a training cycle can disrupt the created identity and routine, triggering feelings of helplessness and depression (Palisch & Merritt, 2018). People who put much emotional effort into their fitness journey feel that the interruption of physical progress can feel like a personal failure. Without further psychological support, these experiences can lead to long-term disengagement from physical activity, creating a cycle of self-doubt (Haugen, 2022).

All these mixed languages and expectations set by the fitness professionals can mitigate or exacerbate their risks. Coaches and trainers who emphasise transformation, discipline or rapid results may unintentionally reinforce thinking patterns of perfectionistic tendencies among their clients (Corrie & Palmer, 2014). In contrast, environments that foster psychological flexibility and are process-oriented tend to work as a buffer against adverse mental health outcomes and promote long-term emotional resilience (Evans et al., 2023).

2.3 Motivation Theories and Mental Health Adaptation

Understanding the fluctuations in mental health across the training journey requires a proper level of engagement with motivational theories and an emphasis on satisfaction with psychological needs. Self-Determination Theory posits that human motivation exists on a continuum from extrinsic to intrinsic, and that fulfilling the needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness promotes engagement and psychological well-being (Teixeira et al., 2012). In the context of fitness training and its stages, people who engage for intrinsic reasons are more likely to experience positive mental health outcomes. In contrast, those motivated externally are more vulnerable to psychological distress (Bevervoorde, 2021).

Prior research by Dawidowicz and Baltac (2025) highlighted the psychological tension between empowerment and vulnerability in female fitness participation, underscoring the importance of resilience, motivation regulation, and autonomy-supportive environments for sustaining long-term wellbeing.

The Transtheoretical Behaviour Change model further highlights how mental health can evolve during fitness participation (Prochaska, 1997). According to this model, participants move through stages of change—pre-contemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, and maintenance—each associated with distinct emotional states and different motivational needs. Relapse or stagnation, common during the various phases of training, can trigger psychological distress if not correctly managed (Liu et al., 2018).

Sport Psychology also offers valuable insights, particularly through resilience frameworks. Psychological resilience—the capacity to adapt positively to

adversity—is a critical factor in navigating the emotional challenges of sustained training (Robson, 2014). Resilience is not a static trait but a dynamic process influenced by coping strategies, social support, and self-perception.

In addition to Self-Determination Theory and the Transtheoretical Model, other motivational frameworks like Achievement Goal Theory can provide additional context for understanding mental health adaptation in training environments. Achievement Goal Theory distinguishes between task-oriented goals, where persons strive for personal improvements, and ego-oriented goals that emphasise outperforming competitors (Hackfort & Schinke, 2020). Research has indicated that task orientations are often linked with greater persistence, satisfaction, and emotional resilience in fitness environments. In contrast, ego orientation is associated with anxiety, fear of failure and disengagement when goals are not achieved.

Another layer of complexity is how motivation is regulated over time, as motivation is not a fixed trait but rather a moving, fluctuating psychological state that can be affected by various external and personal factors, or social comparisons (Đurović et al., 2020). For example, a person may start fitness training for intrinsic reasons, but gradually move towards extrinsic factors over time, particularly if they receive feedback based only on appearance or performance. This transition can lead to internal conflict and reduce the protective effect originally gained from autonomy-based engagement (Pope & Harvey, 2015).

Mental health adaptation by the training process can depend on how a person can adjust and reframe their goals. Goal adjustment theory posits that the capacity to disengage from unattainable goals and re-engage with new, more meaningful goals is critical to maintain psychological well-being during setbacks (Mens et al., 2015). This ability is relevant in the context of fitness training, injuries or life disruptions where rigid adherence to original plans can lead to a situation of frustrations and self-criticism.

Additionally, it is essential to consider how motivational support from various external sources may influence psychological outcomes. Professionals like coaches, personal trainers and peers have crucial roles in shaping motivational climates. Environments that encourage autonomy, reflection and emotional openness are much more likely to sustain intrinsic motivation and promote positive mental health (Papaioannou & Dieter Hackfort, 2014). To put in contrast, environments that put pressure on persons to meet fixed standards or too high performance expectations may increase stress levels and create vulnerabilities

2.4 The Role of Social and Environmental Factors

Physical and digital fitness environments play a role in shaping the form of mental health outcomes during the training journey. Proper supportive environments that emphasise body functionality, effort, and personal growth create better psychological resilience and self-efficacy (Tross et al., 2024). Opposite environments to this that prioritise body look, competition, and performance metrics can create more stress, anxiety and self-objectification.

Social support, especially from peers, coaches and training communities, can act as a protective factor against mental health decline during challenging stages of training (Tross et al., 2024). Positive social interactions can reinforce more adaptive coping mechanisms, normalise setbacks and buffer against feelings of isolation. Toxic fitness culture is characterised by judgments, exclusion or unrealistic standards that can accelerate emotional fatigue and disengagement.

The role of coaches, trainers, and fitness professionals influences the tone and psychological climate of training spaces. Coaches who promote outcomes based solely on looks may unintentionally increase the level of anxiety and reinforce perfectionistic tendencies among their clients (Tiggemann & Zaccardo, 2015). Conversely, trainers who adopt a more holistic approach emphasise self-awareness, body functionality, and psychological safety. They can help clients or participants buffer themselves from mental health risks and improve long-term engagement.

Digital platforms, including fitness apps and social media, provided additional layers of influence. While these tools can enhance motivation and provide educational resources, they also risk applying appearance-related pressures and unrealistic expectations (Feng et al., 2024). The continuity of exposure to curated images of success and transformation can distort self-perception and intensify feelings of inadequacy during natural training phases (Lawrence, 2022).

In addition to the immediate social network, broader cultural narratives embedded in fitness culture and environments contribute to mental health outcomes. Mainstream fitness media often present defined body ideals and equate physical appearance with health, discipline and worthiness. These messages promote internalised appearance norms, especially among women and younger participants, who may come to evaluate their progress or value based on conformity to these ideals instead of intrinsic measures of strength or wellbeing (Kim, 2022). Research has shown that internalising their norms strongly correlates with increased body dissatisfaction, disordered eating behaviours, and social withdrawal in fitness (Brailovskaia & Margraf, 2020).

Intersectionality must also be addressed when evaluating how social and environmental factors affect individuals. Fitness environments are not neutral spaces, but they often reflect dominant sociocultural values that can marginalise certain groups based on their gender, age, race, size, ability or identity (Ross, 2022). People who do not fit into the stereotypical fitness ideals can experience exclusion, microaggressions or a lack of representation; these can contribute to lower self-esteem and increase psychological vulnerability during their fitness journey. Many efforts to foster inclusive, diverse, and body-positive environments are essential in mitigating those risks and ensuring that the mental health benefits of fitness spaces are accessible to all.

Recognising the strong influence of social and environmental factors in physical and digital spaces, fitness professionals and mental health practitioners can better anticipate the psychological challenges that come during training. Promoting inclusive, supportive, and psychologically safe environments is ethically essential but also necessary for facilitating the mental health benefits of long-term fitness participation.

3. Thematic Discussion

3.1 Motivation and Goal Formation

The first phase of the fitness journey is often characterised by increased motivation, emotional optimism, and aspirational goal setting. Persons at this stage usually engage in fitness with a sense of excitement and purpose, being inspired by their health goals, aesthetic desires, lifestyle choices or social influences (Gjestvang, Abrahamsen, et al., 2021). This motivational burst can be reinforced by culturally dominant narratives around self-improvement and transformation, especially those promoted on social media marketing and social platforms (Eime et al., 2023). While this can lead to feelings of empowerment, the psychological experience of early training is highly sensitive to the framing of goals and the type of motivation involved.

Self-Determination Theory suggests that motivation in this initial stage falls and continues between intrinsic and extrinsic factors (Teixeira et al., 2012). When a person is motivated intrinsically, including enjoyment, challenge or a desire to master a discipline, they are more likely to establish a sustainable emotional relationship with exercising (Gaesser et al., 2020). In contrast, persons who are motivated extrinsically may start training to meet external standards like societal beauty norms, peer approval, or fear of judgment. It may effectively trigger behaviour changes in the short term. However, it often lacks the psychological stability required for long-term engagement and can lead to vulnerability when visible results are slow or absent.

The goal formation process can heavily influence mental health outcomes during this phase. Goals that are not realistic, or solely based on appearance, tend to foster perfectionism, anxiety and early discouragement (Vicent et al., 2021). A high number of persons underestimate the time, effort and consistency required to ensure sustainable physical progress, and can experience disappointment or even frustration when early results do not align with their expectations. This cognitive dissonance can lead to negative self-evaluation and a sense of failure, even when objective progress is being made (Cooper, 2019). Conversely, goals that are flexible and process-focused, like improving energy level or consistency, have proved an ability to protect against mental health deterioration and promote sustained motivation.

Social factors also shape the motivational landscapes of the early fitness phase. The presence or absence of encouragement from peers, family or trainers can improve confidence or reinforce self-doubt. Environments that celebrate progress and individual efforts tend more to create a sense of belonging. At the same time, those that emphasise competition, aesthetic or comparison can contribute to pressure, shame, or even being afraid of judgment (Pacholek & Zemková, 2022). Online fitness environments can have a similar effect on early-stage fitness participants who compare themselves to high transformational images and can experience dissatisfaction, regardless of their achievement (Yan et al., 2025).

The motivation and goal formation phase is foundational to behaviour change and emotional and mental resilience throughout the fitness journey. Setting psychologically aligned, flexible and health-centred goals that are supported by intrinsic motivation and affirming environments provides a substantial buffer against the mental health challenges that emerge in later stages. By recognising and addressing the psychological complexity of this phase, trainers and various public health professionals can offer more personalised, emotionally safe entry points into long-term fitness engagement.

3.2 Early Progress and Reinforcement

Following the initial motivational burst, many people enter a phase characterised by noticeable physical improvements, habit formation and increased emotional investment in their training. This stage often happens in the first 4-8 weeks of consistent fitness participation. A sense of reward and accomplishment marks it as initial training goals start to show some results, whether it is improved strength, endurance, energy or body composition (O'Neill, 2025). These early wins often serve

as positive reinforcement, helping to solidify the new behaviour as part of building the new identity.

From a psychological point of view, this stage can be one of the most emotionally validating, as individuals will start associating their efforts with observable outcomes. This further reinforces the self-efficacy, which is a belief in a person's capacity to take practical actions, and can promote an upward trend in motivation, confidence and commitment (ACAR, 2020). The positive emotional feedback from this fitness phase is essential for developing intrinsic motivation, particularly if the training is framed around mastery, skill development, or internal wellbeing rather than external appearance (Rutledge, 2019).

However, this stage also has the potential to be a turning point in the mental health trajectory of fitness engagement. As progress becomes more and more visible, people may begin to raise their expectations, sometimes even changing them from realistic towards perfectionistic or aesthetic-oriented goals (Albinsson et al., 2016). This shift can trigger further psychological strain, especially if the newly created goals are not grounded in the person's long-term sustainability or emotional readiness. For example, a person who starts fitness training for energy and mobility may pursue aggressive weight loss targets or adopt more restrictive behaviours if progress is equated with self-worth (Hoeger et al., 2019).

In addition, positive reinforcement in this stage can sometimes become more tied to external validation. Compliments from others, social media engagement, or comparisons with peers can influence the direction and emotional meaning of the training process (Gusdernawati & Widiyanto, 2021). When a person's worth perception becomes dependent on visible results or social approval, individuals risk becoming vulnerable to mental health challenges, particularly future setbacks.

The early reinforcement phase also presents a unique challenge in balancing momentum with moderation. Enthusiastic trainees can influence and increase training frequency, intensity, or dietary restrictions without proper guidance, believing that more effort will produce faster or better results (Sari et al., 2015). While this is portrayed as an immediate problem, it can contribute to overtraining, injury, or emotional exhaustion if not controlled.

This training stage offers an opportunity to instil long-term psychological tools that support resilience and mental wellness. Various professions can encourage reflective practices, including journaling, value-based goal setting, and body functionality awareness, to help individuals remain more grounded during this upward motivational trend. Interventions that normalise fluctuation, emphasise

process over outcome, and celebrate non-physical benefits help maintain emotional balance and reduce dependence on external feedback (Fong et al., 2018).

3.3 Plateau, Setbacks, and Burnout Risk

After the initial high of motivation and the rewards of early progress, people will encounter a psychological plateau, a stage in the fitness where physical improvements slow down and become less noticeable. This natural and expected phase is often accompanied by feelings of frustration, stagnation and self-doubt (Jett & Gibb, 2016). Physical performance can remain steady or even continue improving at a slower rate. However, the lack of visible or dramatic results can affect emotional momentum, especially for people placing their motivation on body look or performance target (Gelman et al., 2022).

This period represents a critical turning point in the training journey. Individuals can start to question the value of their efforts, reduce their training intensity or stop training altogether. In some cases, this plateau is misinterpreted as failure, leading to lowered confidence and increased risk of maladaptive coping behaviours to manage stress, including compulsive exercise and restrictive dieting (Parker et al., 2024). These psychological responses are more likely in people who are missing a proper support system or who entered the training with strict outcome-focused expectations.

Burnout is a salient risk during this stage. It is often characterised by emotional exhaustion, mental fatigue, and a diminished sense of accomplishment. Exercise burnout can result from sustained overtraining, insufficient rest or unrealistic self-delivered pressure (Oglesby et al., 2020). Unlike simple boredom or demotivation, burnout often comes with psychological withdrawal, irritability, and physical symptoms like chronic fatigue or injury. Research has shown that even recreational athletes and regular fitness people can experience symptoms of burnout, particularly when training becomes more compulsive or overly tied to identity (Cayton & McLeod, 2019).

Social and environmental pressures and stress can impact this phase. Individuals can compare their perceived lack of progress to others, especially in online fitness spaces where various images of transformation dominate the media (Brougham, 2021). This can create a feeling of inadequacy, even if the person maintains healthy and consistent progress. In an environment with group training, the plateau phase can lead to social withdrawal if a person feels embarrassed or isolated.

To prevent psychological decline during this phase, fitness professionals and mental health supporters can play an essential role in reframing expectations and normalising plateaus and setbacks as part of the natural training process. Introducing flexible goal setting, emphasising process over outcome, and reinforcing the value of rest and recovery are key strategies to sustain emotional well-being (Madigan & Nicholls, 2017). Teaching clients to properly recognise early signs of emotional and physical burnout and encouraging them to reflect on their training can restore intrinsic motivation and protect mental health.

When correctly managed with awareness and support, the plateau and setback phase can become a period of growth instead of decline. It will provide a valuable opportunity to recalibrate goals, reconnect with intrinsic values, and develop emotional resilience to support the following stages or long-term fitness engagement.

3.4 Identity Shift and Emotional Integration

In this final stage of the fitness training journey, many individuals undergo a significant psychological transformation in how they perceive themselves, their capabilities and their relationship with physical activity. This identity shift is often gradual and becomes most visible when training transitions from a temporary goal-driven task towards a long-term lifestyle integration. At this point, individuals are beginning to perceive themselves as someone who lives an active life, reflecting at the same time that fitness is part of their personal and social identity (Liuşnea, 2022).

The psychological outcomes during this phase can be highly beneficial. Studies on exercise identity have shown that long-term physical activity engagement is associated with increased psychological resilience, emotional regulation, and a greater sense of autonomy and purpose (Nigg & Durand, 2016). When people view training as part of who they are, instead of doing it only for external rewards or approval, the emotional experience becomes much more stable and fulfilling. This deeper integration supports not only adherence to physical activity but also wider mental health benefits like improved level of confidence, decreased stress and increased emotional coping capacity (Suetani et al., 2017).

However, this fitness stage is not without risks. Developed over-identification with the fitness identity can create a situation of psychological inflexibility. For example, persons who would define themselves too narrowly in the category of performance or physical look can struggle with self-confidence fluctuating during times of sickness, injury or lifestyle disruptions, which may limit fitness training (Rebar & Taylor, 2017). This rigour can create anxiety or distress when training

routines are interrupted, leading potentially to unhealthy behaviours like compulsive exercise or disordered eating in an attempt to preserve the identity.

There is a risk of social disconnection if a person's lifestyle becomes increasingly insular or dominated by fitness-related activities. Individuals with a strong sense of belonging and validation from their fitness circles can find it difficult to relate to others outside of these spaces, leading to subtle isolation or identity doubt (Baker, 2023). These dynamics highlight how important it is to develop a multifaceted identity that includes but is not solely defined by fitness participation (Crocetti & Salmela-Aro, 2018).

Positive outcomes in this training phase are more likely when a person develops emotional literacy about their training. This includes recognising emotional triggers, embracing fluctuations in motivation, and practising compassion towards oneself when goals shift or progress slows down (Zetlin, 2020). Mindfulness, body neutrality, and functional goal settings have emerged as protective strategies that allow individuals to enjoy fitness benefits without becoming psychologically dependent on them.

Professionals working with long-term trainees can help by encouraging reflective practices, celebrating non-performance-based wins, and facilitating discussion around purpose, identity, and balance. When managed well, the identity change and emotional integration stage represents the culmination of psychological growth throughout the fitness journey. In this space, training supports long-term well-being, flexibility, and life satisfaction.

4. Implications for Practice

The findings of this review point out the need for a more psychologically informed approach to fitness training - one that will acknowledge the emotional journey a person goes through during their participation. Recognising the four distinct stages of mental health adaptation, motivation and additionally goal formation, with early progress and reinforcement, moments of plateau and burnout risks and identity integration, allows various professionals to provide stage-specific support that can promote long-term mental wellbeing.

The implications for fitness professionals are clear: coaching cannot be purely based on performance. Trainers do play an essential role in shaping the motivational environment and emotional safety of the fitness field. During the early stages, coaches should encourage realistic, flexible goals and focus on intrinsic motivators like enjoyment, energy, and confidence. Strengthening internal progress over external validation can help prevent early perfectionism and burnout (Russell, 2021).

As people progress, fitness professionals must recognise and normalise the plateau phase rather than see it as failure. This would include educating people on the biological and psychological nature of plateaus, validating their emotional frustration, and introducing appropriate tools to deal with it. Trainers and coaches should also be adequately trained to identify early signs of exercise burnout and maladaptive behaviours, and to be prepared to refer people to a qualified mental health professional when it would be necessary (Bissett et al., 2020). For psychologists and mental health professionals, this model offers a valuable framework for understanding how fitness behaviours evolve emotionally over time. When working with clients who are active or just returning to exercise, clinicians have options to explore the client's current training phase and assess whether their mental health symptoms may be linked to overtraining or unrealistic expectations. Proper intervention techniques connected with self-compassion can be adjusted to support the individual at each training stage.

Public health and wellness program designers can benefit from this framework by incorporating stage-based mental health education into exercise initiatives. Instead of promoting exercise as a universal solution for all, campaigns can embrace the complexity of emotional change, normalise setbacks and offer guidance that aligns with a person's readiness, motivation and experience. Integrating insights into the structure and support of fitness programs is ethical and necessary for sustainable mental and emotional well-being. Meeting people where they are in their training journey and supporting them in each phase can create environments where fitness becomes a tool for growth instead of only a performance metric.

5. Limitations and Future Research

This review provides a structured framework for understanding the psychological stages of mental health adaptation during fitness training. Several limitations should be acknowledged. At first, much of the available literature focuses on either the benefits of physical activity or clinical outcomes related to exercise. Still, fewer studies specifically address psychological transitions across distinct training stages. As a result, this review draws upon research from multiple disciplines - sport psychology, clinical psychology, behavioural health and public health, to assemble a cohesive model. Although this interdisciplinary approach is a strength, it can also limit the depth of analysis for each phase individually, as specific constructs remain under-researched in exercise-specific contexts.

At seconds, this review is based on narrative synthesis instead of systematic or meta-analytic methods. While this allows for theoretical exploration and flexible integration of concepts, it introduces subjectivity and potential bias in the selection and interpretation of sources. A future systematic review or longitudinal

meta-analysis would help validate and refine the proposed four-stage psychological model of fitness training.

Third, much of the literature to date is skewed towards young people and the predominantly Western population, which limits the generalizability of findings. Variables like age, gender identity, cultural backgrounds, socioeconomic status, and disability status can significantly shape how people experience and adapt to fitness training psychologically. Future research should explore how these factors interact with mental health trajectories across diverse populations. Intersectional approaches are particularly needed to capture the experiences of underrepresented groups in fitness and wellness spaces.

In addition, the role of digital technology in shaping psychological outcomes remains a rapidly evolving area. While this review discusses the mental health implications of social media and fitness tracking, there is limited empirical work on how algorithm-driven exposure, online coaching models, and wearable tech affect long-term emotional well-being. These tools can both enhance and hinder mental health, depending on how they are used, moderated or internalised by users. Research that investigates digital influences across different stages of training could offer more targeted guidance for both professionals and participants.

6. Conclusion

This narrative review has explored the psychological evolution that individuals experience in their fitness journey. It pointed out how mental health is not a static outcome of exercise but a dynamic process influenced by motivation, environment, and personal identity. By organising this evolution into four distinct stages - Motivation and Goal Formation, Early Progress and Reinforcement, Plateau and Burnout Risk, Identity Shift and Emotional Integration - this paper offers a structured framework to better understand the emotional complexity of sustained physical activity.

While fitness training is widely celebrated for its physical and mental health benefits, this review emphasises that context, expectations and support systems profoundly shape these outcomes. Early stages are marked by motivation and optimism that can quickly become emotionally taxing if goals are driven by external factors or rooted in perfectionism. Similarly, the plateau phase introduces risks of burnout, self-doubt and disconnection if a person lacks the coping tools or support necessary to process slowed progress. The final stage - identity formation - offers empowerment and risk, depending on whether individuals develop a flexible, health-centred narrative or become over-identified with performance or appearance-based ideas.

Across all stages, the role of psychological safety, social connection and intrinsic motivation is critical. Trainers, coaches, psychologists, and health professionals must move beyond generic exercise prescriptions and adopt a more humanised, emotionally literate approach to physical activity. Supporting clients not only through physical change but also through emotional fluctuation can enhance not just adherence but also long-term mental wellbeing.

This review also pointed out a need for further research that captures the emotional realities of fitness training. Most current studies focus on clinical endpoints or snapshot outcomes, overlooking the nuanced mental states that fluctuate across time. More diverse, intersectional, and digitally aware studies are essential to validate and expand the proposed model.

Finally, fitness should not be prompted only as a path to transformation or performance but as a lifelong relationship between the body and the mind—one that evolves, resets, and redefines itself over time. Embracing the psychological stages of training allows us to meet the person where they are and create systems that support well-being, not just endurance.

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